

Cremation: Is It Ok for the Catholics?

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It was Friday morning.....phone call from Mr. Thomas [name change] saying, Father Can you help us to get the body of my Daddy who died last night? Sasoon hospital authorities are not giving the Body of my father?.....

After 2 days again call saying that they are giving me the ashes of the cremation of my Daddy and told me that put them in the Mula river? Is it ok? What shall we do about the ashes? Can you speak to our parish priest? It happened during the lockdown.

Last month the superior of the religious congregation Sr. Rosemary [name change] asked the ashes of the sister to be put at the foundation of the cross as we are building the cross in her honour as she was the pioneer for this project etc. So there are many questions about the cremation and use of the ashes after the cremation.

Therefore, the Vatican has given the norms called [given by the Congregation for the Doctrine of Faith] Instruction Ad Resurgendum cum Christo regarding the burial of the deceased and the conservation of the ashes in the case of cremation, on 25.10.2016.

The Catholic church is not against cremation but why one wants to be cremated. The church must know the good reason for cremation. Nowadays some religious prefer cremation to burial. The church recommends the burial because, “The resurrection of Jesus is the culminating truth of the Christian faith, preached as an essential part of the Paschal Mystery from the very beginnings of Christianity: “For I handed on to you as of first importance what I also received: that Christ died for our sins in accordance with the scriptures; that he was buried; that he was raised on the third day in accordance with the scriptures; that he appeared to Cephas, then to the Twelve”.....[No.2 of Ad Resurgendum cum Christo].

Jesus was buried. Catholics are expected to be buried. It is the most ancient Catholic tradition, and therefore the church recommends that the bodies of the Catholics be buried in the cemeteries. The Catholic church considers the burial of the dead one of the corporal works of mercy.

“In memory of the death, burial, and resurrection of the Lord, the mystery that illumines the Christian meaning of death, burial is above all the most fitting way to express faith and hope in the resurrection of the body.....[No. 3, of Ad Resurgendum cum Christo].

Canon law clearly states, “The Church earnestly recommends that the pious custom of burial be retained; but it does not forbid cremation, unless this is chosen for reasons which are contrary to Christian teaching [1983 code, C.1176 #3]. Before the 1983 code, the cremation of Catholics was forbidden and there were some penal measures because of French Revolution when cremation had been positively advocated by liberal and atheistic movements etc [1917 code c. 1203,1240]

Funeral rites are to be granted to those who have chosen cremation unless there is evidence that their choice was dictated by anti-Christian motives: “..... since cremation of the deceased’s body does not affect his or her soul, nor does it prevent God, in his omnipotence, from raising up the deceased body to new life. Thus cremation, in and of itself, objectively negates neither the Christian doctrine of the soul’s immortality nor that of the resurrection of the body.....” [No.4’ of Ad Resurgendum cum Christo]. Hence cremation is not prohibited but it is not encouraged.

There should not be a scandal in the community and the appearance of religious indifferentism. Therefore, Christ’s faithful needs to be made aware of it. “When the deceased notoriously has requested cremation and the scattering of their ashes for reasons contrary to the Christian faith, a Christian funeral must be denied to that person according to the norms of the law” [No.8’ of Ad Resurgendum cum Christo].

After the funeral rites, body is cremated, what to do with the ashes: -

- The ashes must be preserved in a cemetery grave; or preserved in a niche in the cemetery
- The ashes cannot be kept at home or scatter in the air or on the water [River/sea/pond]

- In any other way to convert even part of the ashes into, any form of commemorative item like in memento, pieces of jewellery or other objects
- Should not be used for any other purpose.

Hence Ashes of the Catholic faithful has to be disposed of as per the norms of the Catholic Church.

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